
An Examination of Human Rights as A Tool of the United Nations

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ABSTRACT

Human Rights is the latest and newest religion which many nations push as interest to interfere in other countries national interest. Like earlier religions, it is as confusing and misleading to those who claim to be it adhere followers. For instance, non-seem to want to understand the exact doctrine that governs Human Rights.

The paper relied on both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources would be based on oral interviews and archival materials. Secondary sources on the other hand, were included in literatures such as books and newspapers. The oral interviews would be recorded and transcribed for analysis. The documentary data would be subjected to internal and external criticism for authentication and then to textual and contextual analysis

The paper contributed to knowledge through concepts such as Human Rights, which was unique in the 20st century.

KEYWORDS: Human Right, Natural Rights, Declaration, Education, United Nations.

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INTRODUCTION

The world was plunged into two major wars in the opening of the 20th century, the First World War started from 1914-1918 (Leroy, 1980). Major circumstances of the war includes the annexation of Bosnia Herzegovina, the Balkan crisis of 1912 and 1913 respectively, the Agadir crisis of 1911, the final cause of the war was the concept of Nationalism- a popular sentiment that shaped the whole of European history, the murder of Archduke Francis Ferdinand at Sarajevo- the heir apparent to the throne of Austria, thus on the 28 of July Austria declared war on Serbia state, the Entente Cordiale also supported it. The First World War was presumed to be a war that will end all wars, devastation caused millions of casualty, disaster and mal-nutritious, many were rendered homeless. The United Nations (UN) was founded in 1945 in San Francisco by 51 states (Hosti, 2004). It was the successor to the League of Nations, which had failed to effectively counter aggression in the 1950s. Like the League, the UN was founded to increase international order, Human Rights and the rule of law to prevent another World War. Certain tension has long existed between the UN and the United States as the world's most powerful state. (The United States did not join the League, and it was partly to ensure U.S. interest that the UN headquarters was placed in New York). The UN in some ways constrains the United States by creating the one coalition that can rival U.S. power-that of all the states. A certain isolationist streak in U.S. foreign policy runs counter to the UN concept. However, the UN amplifies U.S. power when the United States leads the global UN coalition. The United States is not rich or strong enough to keep order in the world by itself. And, as a great trading nation, the United States benefit from the stability and order that the UN helps create.

In the 1950s and 1960s, the UN's membership more than doubled as colonies in Asia and Africa won independence. This expansion changed the character of the General Assembly, in which each state has one vote regardless of size. The new members had different concerns from those of the Western industrialized countries and in many cases resented having been colonized by Westerners (Calvocoressi, 1968). Many states in the global South believed that the United States enjoyed too much power in the UN. They noticed that the UN is usually effective in international security affairs only when the United States leads the effort (which happens when U.S. interests are at stake).

The growth in membership thus affected voting patterns in the UN. During the UN's first two decades, the General Assembly had regularly sided with the United States, and the Soviet Union was the main power to use its veto in the Security Council to counter balance that tendency. But as newly independent states began to predominate, the United States found itself in the minority on many issues, and by the 1970s and 1980s it had become the main user of the veto.

Until 1971, China's seat on the Security Council (and in the General Assembly) was occupied by the nationalist government on the island of Taiwan, which had lost power in mainland China in 1949. The exclusion of communist China was an exception to the UN principle of universal membership, and in 1971 the Chinese seat was taken from the nationalists and given to the

communist government. Today, the government of Taiwan-which functions autonomously in many international matters despite its formal status as a Chinese province- is not a member of the UN (Hedley, 2007).

Throughout the Cold War, the UN had few successes in international security because the U.S- Soviet conflict prevented consensus. The UN appeared somewhat irrelevant in a world structured by two opposing alliance blocs. A few notable exceptions exist, such as defending South Korea during the Korean War and agreeing to station peacekeeping forces in the Middle East, but the UN did not play central role in solving international conflicts. The General Assembly, with its pre-dominantly third world membership, concentrated on the economic and social problems of poor countries, and these became the main work of the UN.

The United Nations started on a steep downward route from the high expectations that surrounded multilateral concepts as postulated by Woodrow Wilson (Donnelly, *Sovereign Inequality and Hierachy in Anarchy American Power and International Society*, 2006). The global security organization envisaged in the Charter of the United Nations, based on a perpetuation of the victorious alliance against Hitler's Germany, was because of the rapidly developing rift between the Communist states and the capitalist states. The Security Council of the organization continued to ensure maintenance of international peace and security. As a matter of fact, the United Nations had curbed hot wars, although some scholars such Duyile, William Abiodun attributed it not to the United Nations, but to the "balance of terror" between nuclear-armed super-Powers, both of which were likely to be destroyed by any direct conflict (Duyile, 2026). The diplomatic shuttles of Secretary-General U Thant in helping to prevent the 1962 Cuban missile crisis has been negated by some scholars, even though at the time both Super-Powers acknowledged it in writing. Other wars the United Nations became involved includes the Israeli – Palestinian crisis in the Middle East and United States invasion of Iraq amongst others. Secondly, the conscious way the United Nations handled the ideological war between the two Super powers the USA and defunct USSR. The United Nations also serves as a socialization forum where world leaders come together to discuss world issues, transmitted ideas and for addressing critical human problems. The UN despite its ideological challenges established a religion called Human Rights. Human Rights became the moral compass and ethical assessment of members.

METHODOLOGY

The paper relied on both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources would be based on oral interviews and archival materials. The researcher interviewed scholars reputable in the concept of Human Rights. Secondary sources on the other hand, were included in literatures such as books and newspapers. The oral interviews would be recorded and transcribed for analysis. The documentary data would be subjected to internal and external criticism for authentication and then to textual and contextual analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In 1948, the UN General Assembly adopted what is considered the core international document concerning human rights: the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. (UDHR) The UDHR does not have the force of international law, but it sets forth (hoped-for) international norms regarding behavior by governments toward their own citizens and foreigners alike. The declaration roots itself in the principle that violations of human rights upset international order (causing outrage, sparking rebellion, etc.) and in the fact that the UN Charter commits states to respect fundamental freedoms. The declaration proclaims that "all human beings are born free and equal" without regard to race, sex, language, religion, political affiliation, or the status of the territory in which they were born. Concern for humanity was expressed in the work of a commission prepared and the General Assembly adopted the Universal Declaration of Human Right. This document sought to establish a global standard for the value and dignity of individuals and groups that all countries would respect. Further emphasis on the importance of human rights was provided by a later agreement among thirty five European nations, together with the United States and Canada. This agreement was made at an international conference in Helsinki, Finland, 1975. The agreement sought to ensure respect for human rights and freedoms and to promote norms in a wide variety of areas, including banning torture, guaranteeing religious and political freedom, and ensuring the right of economic well-being. Many Scholars would context that the boldest idea inscribed into the UN charter was human rights. In a speech at the United Nations just after the adoption of the Universal Declaration in December 1948, Eleane Roosevelt opined that a "curious grapevine" would spread the ideas the declaration far and wide, an apt metaphor for what has taken place. Steven Pinker also contended and characterized these developments as one of the key indicators of progress, "the humanitarian revolution" and " the rights revolutions". Some scholars had also argued that the knowledge gap for human rights is less deep, substantially identifying and examining the agreement on the Universal Declaration of Human Rights; which in Michael Ignatieff's words, was "designed to create fire walls against barbarism (Ignatieff, 2001)."

Until the end of the Cold War, human rights were an ideological ping pong ball, kicked back and forth in on an international table across the East and West territories. The international game was mainly a shouting match, with attacks and denunciations but little attention to practical issues. The non-meeting of minds produced more heat than light, which affected knowledge gaps. Previously, there was a paucity of data on abuses that were occurring in such places as China and the Soviet Union. Now, a host

of UN and private agencies are devoted to information gathering and dissemination. Moreover, we can learn what is happening in real time because various social media turn virtually anyone with a cell phone into a source of information about the repression in the aftermath of stolen elections in Iran in 2009 or the crushing of dissent in Tahrir Square in 2011, or abuses committed in Syria in 2012 by the Assad regime or by the opposition in Aleppo.

Since the adoption of the UDHR, the UN has opened seven treaties for state signature to further define protections of human rights. Unlike the UDHR, these treaties are legally binding contracts signed by states. Of course, international law is only as good as the enforcement mechanisms behind it. Yet, these seven treaties are important in outlining the basic protections for individuals expected by the international community. Two key treaties are the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights. These two treaties, both of which entered into force in 1976, codify the promises of the UDHR while dividing the list of rights in the UDHR into civil-political and economic-social rights, respectively. These two covenants along with the UDHR, are often referred to as the international Bill of Human Rights

Part of the utility of the two 1966 covenants on human rights, covering both the first and the second generation, lies in requiring signatories to submit periodic reports on the human rights situation in their countries. Therefore, ratifying and bringing the covenants into force does not simply connote acceptance of internationally proclaimed standards. It also entails creation of long-term national infrastructures for the protection and promotion of human rights and the resulting collection of data by national authorities and their submission to the United Nations, which then collates it. The UN's data depository would be difficult to match by another body, although much of the material actually comes from NGO sources. Although nonbinding, the Accords- like the Declaration of Human Rights-sought to establish an international standard for protecting human rights and freedoms. They were a major factor in the quest for democracy in Eastern Europe in recent years. In the absence of means for enforcement of human rights provisions, a private organization known as Amnesty International founded in London in 1961, provides actions by government that are contrary to the Declaration and the Accords.

Links between human rights, on the other hand and development and peace and security, on the other hand, are asserted routinely, but this represent exhortations and empty rhetoric rather than scholarly standards of inquiry and the advancement of knowledge. Moreover, access in such countries as North Korea, Syria, or Zimbabwe remains a challenge to accurately documenting abuses. Speculation is a poor substitute for accurate and independent reporting. Today, NGOs play a key role in efforts to win basic political rights in authoritarian Countries-including a halt to the torture, execution, and imprisonment of those expressing political or religious beliefs. The leading organization pressing this struggle is Amnesty International, an NGO that operates globally to monitor and try to rectify glaring abuses of human rights. Amnesty International has a reputation for impartiality and has criticized abuses in many countries, including the United States. Other groups, such as Human Rights watch, work in a similar way but often with a more regional or national focus. NGOs often provide information and advocacy for UN and other regional organizations that attempt to promote human rights. They essentially serve as a bridge between the global or regional organizations and efforts to promote human rights "on the ground."

The U.S. State Department has actively pursued human rights since the late 1970s. An annual U.S. government report assesses human rights in states around the world. In states where abuses are severe or becoming worse, U.S. foreign aid has been withheld from these states or their armed forces. Currently, Human Right is one of the two main areas of conflict (along with Taiwan) in China's relationship with the United States. Several practices drew criticism; these include imprisoning political opponents of the government, the use of prison labor, and a criminal justice system prone to abuses. According to Amnesty International, China executes more people than the rest of the world combined-thousands each year-sometimes within days of the crime and sometimes for relatively minor crimes.

Conclusion

In the Nigerian Civil war and other chaos that has ensued for instance in that nation, Human Right had lacked the required tool to check governance despite the fact that Nigeria claims democratic governance. The Principal Actors in the Nigerian Civil War can be referred to as the Federal Government of Nigeria under the leadership of Major General Yakubu Gowon on the part of Nigeria. The Biafra side was headed by Lt Colonel Odumegwu Emeka Ojukwu (Duyile, Nature and Impact of Involvement of the Navy in the Nigeria Civil War, 1967-70, 2016); other smaller wars such as the Niger Delta Crisis, Boko Haram crisis, and the Herds Men-Farmer crisis. On Niger Delta crisis, the Ken Saro Wiwa and Ogoni environmental agitation; the Ijaw and Itsekiri crisis, the Ijaw and Ilaje crisis, and some other minor issues encouraged the militancy that erupted in the 21st century. However, strange this could be, these events happened but no person was docked for Human Rights. For instance, during the Ijaw and Itsekiri crisis or the Ijaw and Ilaje crisis; Human Rights were critical but nobody was docked (Duyile, BUHARI ADMINISTRATION AND THE NIGERIAN NIGER-DELTA REGION, 2015 – 2021, 2023). For the Boko Haram crisis, issues that as to do with religious schisms, fanaticism, poverty, modernization...etc were but few factors that engendered the crisis; the war may actually have started in the month of July, 2009, when Mohammed Yusuf was arrested. The real crisis actually began when Boko Haram retaliated by attacking some police station in Maiduguri killing over one hundred people (Duyile, Adu, Jegede, & Buhari, 2020). Human Rights had been somewhat a controversial issue that even those who claim to be its champion had brazenly not respected

it. Judging from the above analyses, Nations had always accepted Human Rights concepts that suit them. They choose some and vehemently deny others. Some governments of some Nations are quick to deny their citizens Rights that may challenge their regime stability. Human Rights should be allowed to citizens in spite of the fact that it could affect their Regimes or even personality interest. These issues have made governments reluctant to adhere strictly to Human Rights ideology and doctrines. Governments also use Human Rights as a reason to intervene in other nations affairs.

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